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FINANCING AND MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL PROJECTS ENSURING TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

2025

This article examines the financing of national projects as the foundation of the socioeconomic development of the Russian Federation. It demonstrates the importance of rational financing for the implementation of national projects that ensure technological progress within the country. It presents the qualitative characteristics of new projects that are most significant for ensuring sustainable economic growth, social protection, and national security of the Russian Federation. The dynamics of budget allocations for national projects implemented since 2025 are analyzed. Areas for the effective implementation of national projects based on an integrated approach to financial support are identified. The role of the state in regulating financial flows and determining the significance of the economic and social components of each national project is highlighted.

Keywords: technological progress, national projects, financial support.

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« » (98,29 %).

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2025

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24,988 %, III — 20152,1 20,222 %.

(11480,2 11,520 %

12

, 2025

■	"	1610,8	6816,8	8154,0	11978,4
■	"	1996,7	12811,0	5696,6	14665,6
■	"	4596,2	806,9	1035,6	7173,4
■	"	216,9	1443,0	2443,2	737,2
■	"	1105,7	2094,7	1047,5	1445,2
■	"	1954,0	929,7	1775,2	7122,5

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 11978,4 . IV) (1610,8 . I

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- , 2025 : « IV 2025 (7122,5 , 60,456 %)».
- « II 2025 (2094,7 , 36,794 %)».
- « III 2025 (2443,2 , 50,477 %)».
- « IV 2025 (7173,4 , 52,699 %)».
- « IV 2025 (14665,6 , 41,699 %)».
- « IV 2025 (11978,4 , 41,941 %)».

2026

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2025 14
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 « 2036 »(« 2030
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 « » — 17,976%.
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26,310%.

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